

Table 1. Yields of selected indigenous rice varieties in Cuu Long Province, 1982.

Water depth (cm)	Variety	Crop-cut sample (no.)	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Freshwater area</i>			
31-50	Lem Lun	13	3.6
	Trang Chum	11	3.3
51-70	Cho Bien	20	3.5
	Trang Chum	13	3.5
	Chet som	15	3.4
	Tay Lieu	13	3.4
<i>5-8 mo freshwater area</i>			
31-50	Lua Phi	23	2.8
51-70	Trang Lun	10	3.4
	Lua Phi	39	2.7

Table 2. Yields of selected indigenous rice varieties in Hau Giang Province, 1983.

Harvest month	Water depth (cm)	Variety	No. of crop-cut samples	Yield (t/ha)
Jan	31-50	Tang Chum	12	4.5
		Trang Phuoc	12	4.2
		Cho Bien	11	3.8
	51-70	Trang Chum	23	4.6
		Trang Phuoc	23	4.2
		Nang Chet	10	3.2
Trang Lun		17	3.1	
71-90	Trang Phuoc	14	4.4	
	Trang Chum	16	3.2	
Feb	51-70	Ba Tuc	10	3.3
		Huyet Rong	22	3.2
		Duoi Trau	19	3.2
	71-90	Duoi Trau	23	2.8
		Mong Chim	12	2.7

In 1983 in Hau Giang, we took 508 samples of varieties (Table 2). Of the varieties harvested in Jan, Trang Chum and Trang Phuoc yielded well at 31-90 cm water depths. Of the late varieties, harvested in Feb, four yielded best. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization AGRONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Root and shoot characters of medium- and long-duration rice genotypes

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We studied variations in the root and shoot characters at different nursery stages in 24 medium-duration (< 140 d) and 35 long-duration (> 140 d) rice genotypes. The nursery was sown in uniform sand at 15-cm interrow spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications in 1982 kharif. The nursery received 0.5-0.22-0.42 kg NPK/100 m² area and was watered daily.

Mean root and shoot performance of medium-duration rices, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Genotype	Root length (cm)			Root dry wt (mg)			Root volume (cm ³)		Shoot dry wt (mg)		
	10 d	20 d	30 d	10 d	20 d	30 d	20 d	30 d	10 d	20 d	30 d
	IR52	4	14	13	15	125	210	0.8	0.8	10	179
IET3116	7	9	12	19	25	50	0.3	0.3	12	51	112
IET7231	8	13	12	12	52	129	0.5	0.6	21	74	255
IR1561-228-3-3	4	7	6	10	31	19	0.2	0.1	15	36	47

Root and shoot performance of long-duration rices. A. P., India.

Sample seedlings were collected from the well-watered nursery with a small digging plate that penetrates 20 cm into the soil. Seedlings were pushed from the soil with balls of compact wet sand adhering to the roots. The sand was washed off in a bucket of water and clean plant samples were obtained without disturbing the root system.

Data were recorded from 3 seedlings per replication per genotype at 10, 20, and 30 d after sowing. Root length was measured from the juncture of the shoot and

root to the tip of the longest root. Root volume was measured by water displacement. Root and shoot portions of each seedling were separated, washed, oven-dried, and weighed. There were significant differences among medium- and long-duration rices for all characters.

Medium-duration IR52 had a prolific root system with maximum root length and volume at 20 d. At 30 d, IET3116 had high root dry weight and IET7231 had high shoot dry weight. IR1561-228-3-3 had low mean values for the characters studied (see

table).

Long-duration IR4422-98-3-6-1 show good root length, root dry weight, and shoot dry weight at 10 d. BPT3291 had maximum expression of root and shoot characters at 20 d. BPT5204 showed maximum root length at 30 d (see figure).

Mean root length and root and shoot dry weight increased with growth duration. The varietal differences in root character should be considered in drought resistance studies. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization GRAIN QUALITY

Genetic stability of crack resistance in rice grains

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Late harvesting and uncontrolled drying cause cracks in rice grains that cause milling losses. We identified crack-resistant (CR) and crack susceptible (CS) varieties by screening rices grown and harvested under controlled conditions. Most high yielding, commercial rices were CS.

We tried to develop CR rices by intravarietal selection of some high yielding varieties. A standard index was developed to measure genetic differences in cracking within a variety. The mean of the percentages of green grains, field-cracked grains, and stress-cracked grains was the index for the first generation and, thereafter, percentage of shelling breakage was used instead of green grains.

Three CR lines — FT-1, FT-12, and FT-81 — were established in varieties Pushpa, Vani, and ES-18. For other varieties tested (Jaya, Mangala, Madhu, Pusa 150, and Intan), genetic variation in crack resistance was either very small or nil and was masked by environmental variations, which prevented intravarietal selection.

The CR lines were identical to their parents in plant, grain, and yield characters (see figure). The genetic stability of the

Cracking resistance of 4 lines isolated through intravarietal selection, Mysore, India. D = Dec, J = Jan.